

Divergent effects of entomopathogenic fungi and medicinal mushroom species on *Drosophila melanogaster* lifespan

Real-time death record of flies

All the entomopathogenic fungi and mushroom species showed different death record of flies in their 5 plate replicates. The daily number of dead flies was recorded and mentioned in **Table 1** to **Table 6**.

Table 1: Daily death record of flies treated with *Fusarium verticillioides* species.

Day	<i>Fusarium verticillioides</i>				
	Plate 1	Plate 2	Plate 3	Plate 4	Plate 5
1	0 dead				
2	0 dead				
3	0 dead				
4	0 dead				
5	2 dead	1 dead	1 dead	2 dead	0 dead
6	2 dead	2 dead	1 dead	2 dead	1 dead
7	2 dead	2 dead	3 dead	3 dead	2 dead
8	5 dead	4 dead	3 dead	4 dead	2 dead
9	9 dead	14 dead	13 dead	8 dead	10 dead
10	13 dead	18 dead	19 dead	14 dead	16 dead
11	18 dead	18 dead	19 dead	17 dead	16 dead
12	19 dead	20 dead	20 dead	19 dead	16 dead
13	19 dead	20 dead	20 dead	19 dead	18 dead
14	20 dead	20 dead	20 dead	20 dead	19 dead
15	20 dead				

Table 2: Daily death record of flies treated with *Fusarium oxysporum* species.

Day	<i>Fusarium</i>	<i>Fusarium</i>	<i>Fusarium</i>	<i>Fusarium</i>	<i>Fusarium</i>
	<i>oxysporum</i>	<i>oxysporum</i>	<i>oxysporum</i>	<i>oxysporum</i>	<i>oxysporum</i>
	Plate 1	Plate 2	Plate 3	Plate 4	Plate 5
1	0 dead				
2	0 dead				
3	0 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead	0 dead
4	0 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead	0 dead
5	0 dead	2 dead	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead
6	0 dead	4 dead	4 dead	2 dead	3 dead
7	0 dead	6 dead	6 dead	4 dead	4 dead
8	1 dead	6 dead	6 dead	5 dead	4 dead
9	4 dead	6 dead	7 dead	6 dead	5 dead
10	8 dead	10 dead	7 dead	8 dead	9 dead
11	16 dead	14 dead	13 dead	11 dead	13 dead
12	17 dead	16 dead	13 dead	16 dead	15 dead
13	20 dead	18 dead	17 dead	19 dead	17 dead
14	20 dead	20 dead	20 dead	19 dead	19 dead
15	20 dead	20 dead	20 dead	20 dead	19 dead
16	20 dead				

Table 3: Daily death record of flies treated with *Aspergillus flavus* species.

Day	<i>Aspergillus</i>	<i>Aspergillus</i>	<i>Aspergillus</i>	<i>Aspergillus</i>	<i>Aspergillus</i>
	<i>flavus</i>	<i>flavus</i>	<i>flavus</i>	<i>flavus</i>	<i>flavus</i>
	Plate 1	Plate 2	Plate 3	Plate 4	Plate 5
1	0 dead				
2	0 dead				
3	0 dead				
4	0 dead				
5	0 dead	0 dead	0 dead	0 dead	1 dead
6	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead	0 dead	1 dead
7	1 dead	1 dead	0 dead	2 dead	3 dead
8	1 dead	1 dead	0 dead	3 dead	4 dead
9	2 dead	1 dead	0 dead	3 dead	4 dead
10	3 dead	1 dead	1 dead	9 dead	5 dead

11	13 dead	1 dead	3 dead	11 dead	9 dead
12	16 dead	5 dead	10 dead	16 dead	13 dead
13	18 dead	7 dead	13 dead	18 dead	16 dead
14	19 dead	16 dead	20 dead	20 dead	19 dead
15	20 dead	18 dead	20 dead	20 dead	20 dead
16	20 dead				

Table 4: Daily death record of flies treated with *Fusarium brachygibbosum* species.

Day	<i>Fusarium</i>	<i>Fusarium</i>	<i>Fusarium</i>	<i>Fusarium</i>	<i>Fusarium</i>
	<i>brachygibbosum</i>	<i>brachygibbosum</i>	<i>brachygibbosum</i>	<i>brachygibbosum</i>	<i>brachygibbosum</i>
	Plate 1	Plate 2	Plate 3	Plate 4	Plate 5
1	0 dead				
2	0 dead				
3	0 dead	0 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead
4	0 dead	0 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead
5	0 dead	1 dead	3 dead	2 dead	1 dead
6	0 dead	2 dead	5 dead	4 dead	2 dead
7	0 dead	3 dead	5 dead	4 dead	3 dead
8	1 dead	3 dead	8 dead	6 dead	5 dead
9	13 dead	4 dead	10 dead	8 dead	6 dead
10	15 dead	6 dead	11 dead	10 dead	9 dead
11	16 dead	9 dead	15 dead	13 dead	13 dead
12	16 dead	13 dead	15 dead	13 dead	15 dead
13	18 dead	14 dead	15 dead	15 dead	16 dead
14	18 dead	14 dead	15 dead	16 dead	16 dead
15	18 dead	16 dead	16 dead	16 dead	17 dead
16	20 dead	18 dead	16 dead	17 dead	17 dead
17	20 dead	19 dead	18 dead	20 dead	18 dead
18	20 dead	19 dead	18 dead	20 dead	20 dead
19	20 dead	19 dead	20 dead	20 dead	20 dead
20	20 dead				

Table 5: Daily death record of flies in the control group.

Day	Control Group Plate 1	Control Group Plate 2	Control Group Plate 3	Control Group Plate 4	Control Group Plate 5
1	0 dead				
2	0 dead				
3	0 dead				
4	0 dead				
5	0 dead				
6	0 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead
7	0 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead
8	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead
9	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead
10	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead	2 dead
11	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead	2 dead
12	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead	1 dead	2 dead
13	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead	1 dead	3 dead
14	1 dead	0 dead	1 dead	1 dead	4 dead
15	2 dead	1 dead	2 dead	3 dead	4 dead
16	2 dead	1 dead	2 dead	3 dead	4 dead
17	2 dead	1 dead	2 dead	3 dead	4 dead
18	2 dead	1 dead	2 dead	3 dead	5 dead
19	2 dead	2 dead	2 dead	3 dead	5 dead
20	2 dead	2 dead	2 dead	5 dead	6 dead
21	2 dead	2 dead	3 dead	5 dead	6 dead
22	2 dead	2 dead	3 dead	5 dead	6 dead
23	2 dead	3 dead	3 dead	5 dead	6 dead
24	3 dead	3 dead	3 dead	6 dead	7 dead
25	3 dead	4 dead	4 dead	6 dead	7 dead
26	3 dead	4 dead	4 dead	6 dead	9 dead
27	4 dead	5 dead	4 dead	6 dead	10 dead
28	4 dead	5 dead	5 dead	7 dead	10 dead
29	4 dead	6 dead	6 dead	7 dead	11 dead
30	6 dead	6 dead	6 dead	8 dead	11 dead
31	6 dead	7 dead	8 dead	8 dead	11 dead

32	6 dead	7 dead	8 dead	8 dead	11 dead
33	7 dead	9 dead	10 dead	8 dead	12 dead
34	8 dead	10 dead	11 dead	9 dead	12 dead
35	8 dead	10 dead	11 dead	9 dead	13 dead
36	10 dead	11 dead	12 dead	10 dead	15 dead
37	11 dead	12 dead	13 dead	10 dead	15 dead
38	11 dead	12 dead	14 dead	11 dead	17 dead
39	11 dead	13 dead	16 dead	14 dead	18 dead
40	14 dead	17 dead	18 dead	16 dead	20 dead
41	16 dead	18 dead	20 dead	17 dead	20 dead
42	20 dead	20 dead	20 dead	18 dead	20 dead
43	20 dead				

Table 6: Daily death record of flies treated with *Lentinula edodes* species.

Day	<i>Lentinula edodes</i> Plate 1	<i>Lentinula edodes</i> Plate 2	<i>Lentinula edodes</i> Plate 3	<i>Lentinula edodes</i> Plate 4	<i>Lentinula edodes</i> Plate 5
1	0 dead				
2	0 dead				
3	0 dead				
4	0 dead				
5	0 dead				
6	0 dead				
7	0 dead				
8	0 dead				
9	0 dead	0 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead
10	1 dead	0 dead	0 dead	1 dead	0 dead
11	2 dead	0 dead	0 dead	1 dead	1 dead
12	2 dead	0 dead	1 dead	1 dead	1 dead
13	3 dead	0 dead	1 dead	1 dead	1 dead
14	3 dead	1 dead	1 dead	1 dead	1 dead
15	3 dead	1 dead	1 dead	2 dead	2 dead
16	4 dead	1 dead	2 dead	2 dead	2 dead
17	4 dead	2 dead	2 dead	2 dead	2 dead

18	4 dead	2 dead	2 dead	3 dead	2 dead
19	4 dead	3 dead	2 dead	3 dead	2 dead
20	4 dead	3 dead	2 dead	3 dead	3 dead
21	4 dead	3 dead	2 dead	3 dead	3 dead
22	4 dead	3 dead	2 dead	3 dead	3 dead
23	6 dead	3 dead	3 dead	3 dead	3 dead
24	6 dead	3 dead	3 dead	4 dead	3 dead
25	6 dead	4 dead	3 dead	4 dead	3 dead
26	6 dead	4 dead	3 dead	5 dead	4 dead
27	6 dead	5 dead	3 dead	5 dead	4 dead
28	6 dead	6 dead	3 dead	5 dead	4 dead
29	7 dead	6 dead	4 dead	5 dead	4 dead
30	7 dead	6 dead	4 dead	5 dead	6 dead
31	7 dead	6 dead	5 dead	7 dead	6 dead
32	7 dead	6 dead	5 dead	7 dead	7 dead
33	8 dead	6 dead	6 dead	7 dead	8 dead
34	8 dead	7 dead	6 dead	7 dead	8 dead
35	8 dead	7 dead	6 dead	9 dead	8 dead
36	8 dead	8 dead	9 dead	9 dead	10 dead
37	8 dead	8 dead	10 dead	10 dead	10 dead
38	8 dead	8 dead	11 dead	10 dead	10 dead
39	9 dead	10 dead	11 dead	10 dead	10 dead
40	10 dead	10 dead	11 dead	11 dead	12 dead
41	10 dead	10 dead	11 dead	11 dead	12 dead
42	10 dead	11 dead	12 dead	13 dead	12 dead
43	10 dead	11 dead	12 dead	13 dead	12 dead
44	10 dead	11 dead	12 dead	14 dead	13 dead
45	10 dead	11 dead	13 dead	14 dead	13 dead
46	11 dead	12 dead	13 dead	14 dead	13 dead
47	11 dead	13 dead	14 dead	15 dead	14 dead
48	11 dead	13 dead	15 dead	16 dead	15 dead
49	11 dead	14 dead	15 dead	17 dead	16 dead
50	14 dead	15 dead	16 dead	17 dead	16 dead
51	16 dead	15 dead	18 dead	17 dead	17 dead

52	17 dead	17 dead	18 dead	18 dead	17 dead
53	18 dead	19 dead	20 dead	19 dead	18 dead
54	20 dead	19 dead	20 dead	20 dead	19 dead
55	20 dead				